

Metric or Indicator	Data Quality Dimension	Article References	Years	ISO 25012 Category	Number of Articles		Data Quality Dimension	Number of Metrics per Dimension	Number of articles where the dimension appears
Conformity Format (Consistency with standard patterns)	Consistency	1, 2, 4, 6, 8, 12, 13, 16, 18, 21, 23, 25, 27, 28, 29, 32, 34, 38, 39, 40, 43, 45, 47, 49, 52, 53, 709, 722, 735, 736, 792	2002, 2002, 2003, 2004, 2009, 2011, 2012, 2014, 2014, 2015, 2017, 2017, 2018, 2019, 2020, 2021, 2022, 2022, 2022, 2023, 2023, 2023, 2024, 2024, 2025, 2025, 2025, 2025, 2025, 2025	Inherent	31		Consistency	13	42
% of null/missing values	Completeness	2, 6, 8, 13, 18, 21, 24, 25, 28, 29, 31, 40, 43, 45, 47, 48, 49, 53, 736, 792, 794	2002, 2002, 2003, 2009, 2012, 2012, 2014, 2014, 2017, 2018, 2018, 2018, 2019, 2021, 2022, 2023, 2024, 2025, 2025, 2025, 2025	Inherent	21		Completeness	6	44
Redundancy detection (duplicate rows/columns)	Uniqueness	1, 2, 4, 8, 12, 13, 16, 18, 20, 23, 24, 31, 32, 34, 39, 40, 47, 48, 736, 792, 794	2002, 2003, 2009, 2011, 2012, 2014, 2015, 2017, 2018, 2018, 2018, 2020, 2022, 2022, 2023, 2023, 2023, 2023, 2025, 2025, 2025	Inherent	21		Uniqueness	2	22
% of correct values	Accuracy	1, 6, 8, 17, 21, 24, 29, 36, 40, 49, 52, 53, 722, 736, 751, 792	2002, 2002, 2004, 2010, 2012, 2012, 2017, 2018, 2019, 2019, 2021, 2024, 2025, 2025, 2025, 2025	Inherent	16		Accuracy	11	33
Update frequency	Timeliness	17, 24, 31, 34, 40, 43, 47, 49, 792	2002, 2009, 2017, 2018, 2018, 2019, 2020, 2023, 2025	System-dependent	9		Timeliness	8	18
% of cell completeness	Completeness	1, 4, 6, 8, 12, 17, 49, 794	2002, 2002, 2017, 2019, 2022, 2023, 2024, 2025	Inherent	8		Validity	3	6
% of variable/column completeness	Completeness	4, 12, 16, 20, 24, 44, 49	2002, 2012, 2012, 2022, 2022, 2023, 2023	Inherent	7		Accessibility	5	5
Ratios of accurate/non-duplicate entries	Accuracy	2, 45, 48, 49	2002, 2014, 2018, 2023	Inherent	4		Interpretability	4	5
% of tuple/row completeness	Completeness	1, 4, 12, 20	2017, 2022, 2023, 2023	Inherent	4		Usability	2	2
Outlier detection	Accuracy	4, 36, 40, 794	2018, 2023, 2024, 2025	Inherent	4				
Range	Accuracy	12	2022	Inherent	1		Total geral	54	177
Anomaly validation rates	Validity	32, 40, 45, 53	2011, 2012, 2014, 2015	System-dependent	4				
Protection/Faithfulness	Consistency	709	2025	System-dependent	1				
Documentation presence	Completeness	19, 34, 49	2002, 2011, 2023	Inherent	3				
Temporal trends	Timeliness	19, 38, 49	2002, 2011, 2024	System-dependent	3				
Invalid addresses	Accuracy	13, 18	2003, 2014	Inherent	2				
Metadata presence	Interpretability	4, 11	2023, 2023	Inherent	2				
Runtime efficiency	Performance	9, 34	2010, 2023	System-dependent	2				
Ropen (Resource Openness)	Accessibility	3	2021	System-dependent	1				
Machine readability (via five-star rating)	Accessibility	4	2023	System-dependent	1				

Accessible URLs	Accessibility	20	2023	System-dependent	1				
Dereferenceability	Accessibility	41	2016	System-dependent	1				
Ease of data attainability	Accessibility	49	2002	System-dependent	1				
Confidence interval	Accuracy	12	2022	Inherent	1				
Proportion of implausible z-scores	Accuracy	27	2022	Inherent	1				
Accuracy of image-generated descriptions	Accuracy	28	2025	System-dependent	1				
Proportion of correct labels through manual inspection	Accuracy	34	2023	Inherent	1				
Discrepancies across datasets	Accuracy	44	2012	Inherent	1				
Potential data manipulation	Authenticity	25	2022	System-dependent	1				
Credibility of the data source	Believability	49	2002	System-dependent	1				
Percentage of unknowns	Completeness	6	2024	Inherent	1				
Conformity Names	Conformity	12	2022	System-dependent	1				
Rlink (Linkage)	Consistency	3	2021	System-dependent	1				
Frequency of multilingual inconsistencies	Consistency	16	2022	System-dependent	1				
Usage Consistency across layers	Consistency	19	2011	System-dependent	1				
Edit distance for term similarity	Consistency	19	2011	System-dependent	1				
Cronbach's Alpha coefficient	Consistency	27	2022	System-dependent	1				
Schema evolution signals	Consistency	32	2011	System-dependent	1				
Satisfiability	Consistency	39	2015	System-dependent	1				
Repair cost functions	Consistency	39	2015	System-dependent	1				
Misreported Content Type	Consistency	41		System-dependent	1				
Member of Disjoint Classes	Consistency	41	2016	Inherent	1				
Rmr (Metadata Richness)	Interpretability	3	2016	Inherent	1				
Rmnr (Metadata Richness Normalized)	Interpretability	3	2021	Inherent	1				
Metadata understandability	Interpretability	11	2023	System-dependent	1				
Implication complexity	Consistency	39	2015	System-dependent	1				
Links to External Data Providers	Linkage	41	2016	System-dependent	1				
Good Interlinks	Linkage	41	2016	System-dependent	1				
Traceability	Provenance	19	2011	System-dependent	1				

Rrdf RDF (Availability)	Readability	3	2021	System-dependent	1				
Metadata confidentiality	Security	11	2023	System-dependent	1				
Delay calculations (publication/content timeliness)	Timeliness	3	2021	System-dependent	1				
Speed of anomaly correction	Timeliness	32	2011	System-dependent	1				
Volatility	Timeliness	49	2002	System-dependent	1				
Delivery time	Timeliness	49	2002	System-dependent	1				
Input time	Timeliness	49	2002	System-dependent	1				
Age	Timeliness	49	2002	System-dependent	1				
Extensional Conciseness	Uniqueness	41	2016	Inherent	1				
Usage score (based on public ratings)	Usability	4	2023	System-dependent	1				
Fitness for use	Usability	43	2017	System-dependent	1				
Anomaly class labels	Validity	53	2012	System-dependent	1				
Certainty of fixes	Validity	39	2015	System-dependent	1				
disclosure risk (privacy)	Accuracy	784	2025	System-dependent	1				
very specific, will not be considered									
Precision (PPV)	Consistency	9, 36, 46		System-dependent					
Recall	Consistency	9, 36, 46		System-dependent					
F1-score	Consistency	9, 36, 46		System-dependent					
Accuracy	Consistency	46		System-dependent					
Specificity	Consistency	46		System-dependent					
Negative Predictive Value (NPV)	Consistency	46		System-dependent					
AUC (Area Under the Curve)	Consistency	46		System-dependent					
Confusion Matrix	Consistency	36		System-dependent					
				New metrics					
				context-dependent					
				not quality metric					